

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: YUNUS****FIRST NAME: ABDUL MANAF****PROGRAM CODE: DCTD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)*The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:*The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2019 on Windows 10)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Is it necessary that the title is consistent with the research question, and what are the components of a dissertation title?
 - The title does not have to be consistent with the research question. The components of the dissertation title include the name of the author, acknowledgment of the supervisor, hypothesis, and sample.
 - It is important that the title is consistent with the research question, and the components of the dissertation title include treatment, variables, participants, and setting for the research.¹**

¹ James P Sampson Jr, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second edition (Tallahassee, Florida: Florida State University, 2017), 24.

- The title must be consistent with the research question. The components of the dissertation title include the name of the author, research question, readers, and sample.
 - The title does not have to be consistent with the research question. The components of the dissertation title include the research question, supervisor acknowledgment, sample, and setting of research.
2. Which of the following situations does not require that a researcher provide citations?
- When a researcher emphasizes individual numbers and forces readers to infer relationships or trends.**²
 - When a researcher quotes exact words from a source.
 - When a researcher paraphrases ideas that are associated with a specific source, even if you don't quote exact words from it.
 - When a researcher uses any ideas, data, or methods attributable to any source they consulted.
3. How did Torraco (2005) define an integrative literature review?
- A form of research that reviews, critiques, and synthesizes representative literature on a topic in an integrated way such that new frameworks and perspectives on the topic are generated.**³

² Kate L Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations*, Ninth edition (Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 140.

³ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 4th ed. (Los Angeles, London, New Delhi, Singapore, Washington DC, Melbourne: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2019), 352.

- A literature review that provides a broader summary of the literature and includes findings from a range of research designs.
 - A description, summary, and critical evaluation of scholarly works on a certain topic.
 - A review that allows researchers to go beyond the analysis and synthesis of primary research findings and provides new insights and summarized knowledge about a specific topic.
4. Which of the following is true for qualitative research?
- Qualitative research seeks to understand the causal relationship between variables through testing hypotheses.
 - There are no predefined variables for focus analysis, as there are in quantitative research.**⁴
 - Data analysis in qualitative research does not require the researcher to be patient and reflective in a process that strives to make sense of multiple data sources.
 - Quantitative data analysis is the process of bringing order, structure, and meaning to the masses of data collected.
5. How are the limitations of research different from the delimitations of research?
- Limitations are the things that the scope of the research aims and research questions will and will not include, whereas delimitations are the weaknesses of the study based on factors that are often outside of the control of the researcher.

⁴ Ibid., 353.

- Limitations are anticipated constraints in the interpretation of the findings of the dissertation, whereas delimitations are unanticipated constraints in data interpretation.
- Limitations are the boundaries that the researcher sets in a research study, deciding what to include and what to exclude, whereas delimitations are the elements of methodology or study design that impact the interpretation of your research results.
- Limitations are unanticipated constraints in data interpretation, whereas delimitations are anticipated constraints in the interpretation of the findings of the dissertation.**⁵

6. Commas are used

- to make an important distinction between ‘defining’ and ‘non-defining’ relative clauses.**⁶
- to defuse when a phrase introducing or adding to the information in a sentence has a separate emphasis of its own.
- to unite two clauses linked by a conjunction.
- in a list of three or more items, a comma is used to bring them together.

7. Under the Turabian style, how does one cite a book with one (1) author plus an editor in the notes and bibliography?

⁵ Sampson Jr, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 49.

⁶ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission* (European Commission, 2021), 11.

- Author's Last and First Names, *Title of Book: Subtitle of Book*, ed. Editor's First and Last Names (Place of Publication: Publisher's Name, Date of Publication), Pages.
- Author's First and Last Names, *Title of Book: Subtitle of Book*, ed. Editor's First and Last Names (Place of Publication: Publisher's Name, Date of Publication), Pages.**⁷
- Author's First and Last Names, Date of Publication, Title of Book: Subtitle of Book, ed. Editor's First and Last Names (Place of Publication: Publisher's Name), Pages.
- Author's Last and First Names, Title of Book: Subtitle of Book, ed. Editor's First and Last Names, Pages, Date of Publication (Place of Publication: Publisher's Name).
8. How is the European Union's opening text of directives, regulations, and decisions unique?
- The preambles to directives, regulations, and decisions start with a line in capitals, identifying the institution, and ending with a comma.**⁸
- The preambles to directives, regulations, and decisions start with the first letter in capitals, identify the institution, and end with a full stop.

⁷ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations*, 151.

⁸ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 82.

- The preambles to directives, regulations, and decisions start just as all other texts outside the European Union do.
- The preambles to directives, regulations, and decisions start with a line in capitals identifying the institution and ending with a full stop.

9. What is the purpose of the introduction chapter of a dissertation?

- The introduction presents the findings and conclusions of the dissertation.
- The introduction sets the stage for the study and directs readers to the purpose and context of the dissertation.**⁹
- The introduction sets the stage for the problem statement and ensures all aspects of the dissertation are categorized.
- The introduction presents a summary of the dissertation and a definition of the theories used in the dissertation.

10. What is the ideal thing to do if no hypotheses were used in the dissertation research?

- Describe the data analysis techniques that were not used but were relevant to each research question.
- Describe the different data analysis techniques that were not used to test the next hypothesis.
- Describe the data analysis techniques that were used for answering each research question.**¹⁰

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 74.

¹⁰ Sampson Jr, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 48.

- Describe the data analysis techniques that were used to test distinguishable hypotheses.

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